

Preregistration: Emotional and cognitive responses to anatomical human preparations in an exhibition setting

1) Have any data been collected for this study already?

No, no data have been collected for this study yet.

2) What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

The study investigates visitors' emotional and cognitive responses to anatomical human preparations in an exhibition setting. Specifically, it examines whether there are systematic differences in the emotional responses to healthy versus pathological (diseased) human organ specimens, and how viewers process and reflect on these objects cognitively.

Main hypothesis: Diseased specimens will elicit significantly more negative and fewer positive emotional responses compared to healthy ones, with a medium effect size.

3) Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

Emotional effect: Measured via a multiple-choice scale adapted from the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) and additional items. Ten discrete emotions are assessed per specimen, including six negative and four positive emotions. Items are rated individually on a five-point scale. For each participant, responses to the positive and negative emotions will be averaged separately to form two subscale scores. These subscale scores will then be aggregated across all participants and compared between healthy and pathological preparations.

In addition, each individual emotion will be analyzed descriptively across all participants for each organ specimen.

Cognitive effect: Measured through multiple-choice items presented after each object. Participants select statements that apply to their experience (e.g., "I learned something about the organ and its diseases"). These are analyzed item-wise.

4) How many and which conditions will participants be assigned to?

All participants will view the same sequence of twelve anatomical specimens (first six healthy, last six pathological).

5) Specify exactly which analyses you will conduct to examine the main question/hypothesis.

Mean scores across the emotional items will be calculated separately for the healthy and pathological objects (positive and negative subscales). These means will be compared using paired-samples t-tests.

6) Describe exactly how outliers will be defined and handled, and your precise rule(s) for excluding observations.

Participants are excluded who

- are younger than 16 years old.

7) How many observations will be collected or what will determine sample size? No need to justify decision, but be precise about exactly how the number will be determined.

To the best of our knowledge, not a lot of prior studies have examined the immediate emotional and cognitive effects of human anatomical preparations in a museum setting. Assuming a medium effect size ($f = 0.25$), an a priori power analysis using G*Power (power = .80, alpha = .05) suggests a required sample size of **n = 101** participants.

8) Anything else you would like to pre-register? (e.g., secondary analyses, variables collected for exploratory purposes, unusual analyses planned?)

- **Sociodemographic variables** will be collected: age, gender, religion, highest level of education, prior medical knowledge.
- **Exploratory variables:** Attitudes towards age restrictions, photography bans in exhibitions and acceptable conditions for displaying human specimens
- **Additional analyses:** Differences in emotional reactions across individual emotions and object types will be visualized and explored as well as cognitive responses